

BUSINESS ANALYSIS OF TOMATO IN NAGPUR DISTRICT

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Abstract

The current research was conducted in Nagpur District of Maharashtra, to study the marketing of Tomato, challenges faced by the producers in marketing and consumers purchasing behaviours for Tomatoes. A total of 60 vegetable producers, 5 wholesalers and Retailers, 10 producers and consumers were chosen in Research location. The data was gathered by personal interview method, Using multistage random sampling method for the year (2023 – 2024). The 10 villages of 2 tehsils viz., Katol and Narkhed where randomly selected. The research determined three distinct marketing channels for Tomato vegetable. Although channel-I (producer to consumer) proved to be the most effective marketing channel for the selected vegetable, sales volume through this channel were surprisingly low. The price spread for Tomato across all selected channels excluding channel-I was approximately 60-70 percent. The Acharya method was employed to determine marketing efficiency, revealing a decline in efficiency corresponding to an increase in the number of intermediaries. High transportation costs was the major constraint in marketing of vegetable followed by excessive fees by market middlemen, unmetalled roads, packaging material scarcity etc. Blemish-free Tomato was the major expectation reported by the Tomato consumers followed by fresh Tomatoes, Tomatoes at affordable prices etc.

Keywords: Tomato, Acharya method, Price Spread, Marketing Efficiency, Constraints, Expectations

Introduction and Objectives

Agriculture is the foundation of India, supporting 70 percent of the population. Agriculture Marketing combines agriculture (utilizing natural resources for human benefit) with marketing (moving goods from source to consumer). Agricultural marketing covers key area like channels, marketing functions, costs, prices, agencies and market integration, linking the farm sector to the broader economy. Global Tomato production was approximately 189 million metric tones. China led the world in Tomato production, accounting for nearly 39 percent of the global total, solidifying its position as the largest producer. And the top Tomato producing countries, after China, were India, Turkey, and the United States. Andhra Pradesh led India in Tomato production, contributing 20.2 percent to the national total. And the top Tomato producing states, after Andhra Pradesh, were Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Gujarat, and Maharashtra. Tomato cultivation in Maharashtra is prominent in several regions, including Narayangaon near Pune, Nashik, Beed, and Pusegaon among other key areas where farmers actively grow this crop. Narayangaon approximately 18,000 acres are dedicated to Tomato farming yielding around 1,400 tones daily, Pimpalgaon about 40,000 hectares are planted with Tomato and Nashik District about 1.25 lakh hectares, making it a major hub for Tomato production. Nagpur Tomato production enjoys a significant market presence, with extensive distribution networks spanning domestic and neighbouring state markets. Vegetable crops offer tremendous potential for enhancing farmer's income. Vegetable production is characterized by seasonality and exposed to numerous uncertainties, necessitating prompt and efficient marketing strategies. This leads to a multitude of issues for vegetable cultivators. Insufficient transportation infrastructure, limited storage capacity in the market etc. Given the complexities of vegetable marketing, particularly the challenges faced by producers and dynamic consumers purchasing behaviours for Tomatoes. The current research was undertaken to achieve the following specific objectives.

1) To examine the present marketing channel in addition to Marketing Cost, Margins, Price Spread, Marketing Efficiency of Tomato vegetable.

2) To identify the constraints faced by producers in marketing of Tomato vegetable.

3) To assess the purchasing preferences of Tomato consumers.

Materials and Methods

The present study was undertaken in Nagpur District of Maharashtra. This District was deliberately chosen due to its extensive area under Tomato cultivation. Multistage Stratified Random Sampling technique implemented for selection of tehsils, villages and farmers. Initially, Nagpur District was selected as the study location. In the second stage 2 talukas were chosen for Tomato vegetable. The third stage involved

random selection of five villages from the identify talukas followed by random sampling of 6 farmers from each village. Consequently, a total of 60 vegetable producers were selected for gathering the necessary data for the study. The fourth stage involved collecting data on vegetable marketing from a random sample of 5 Wholesalers and Retailers (10 total) in the pre identified tehsils of Nagpur District. In fifth stage the data is collected on marketing constraints and consumer behaviour from a random sample of 10 producers and 10 consumers (20 total) in the previously identified tehsil of Nagpur District.

Analytical Tools :-**D) Price Spread (PS)**

This illustrates the difference between the net price received by the producer and the price paid by the final consumer.

$$PS = RP - PNP$$

Where,

RP =Retailer selling price

PNP = Producer's net price

E) Producer's Share in Consumer's Rupee :-

The producer's share in consumer rupee describes the price margin between the farm level and the retail level for the produce, by applying the following formula.

$$PS = \frac{PF}{PR} \times 100$$

Where,

PS = Producer's share.

PF = Price received by the farmer

PR = Retail price paid by the consumer.

Marketing Efficiency :-

Acharya Agrawal modified method were used to analyze the Tomato marketing efficiency. The formula for determining marketing efficiency is as follows.

$$ME = \frac{FP}{MC + MM}$$

Where,

ME = Marketing efficiency

FP = Net price received by the producer – seller

MC = Total marketing cost

MM = Net marketing margin

Results and Discussion**Marketing cost and Market margins of Tomato vegetable**

The direct marketing channel, where producer sell directly to consumers, eliminates intermediaries, allowing consumers to purchase the desired quantity of selected vegetables at the lowest possible marketing cost. Table No.1 Represent the total marketing cost incurred by Producer was Rs.171/- quintal, Wholesaler was Rs.126/- quintal and Retailer was Rs.85/- quintal in the marketing of Tomato. The Retailers

margin in channel II, and channel III were calculated as Rs. 347/- quintal and Rs. 211/- quintal respectively. The wholesaler margin in channel III was Rs. 130 /- quintal. The prices paid by consumer were Rs. 1800 /- quintal in channel I, Rs. 2056/-quintal in channel II and Rs.1752 /- quintal in channel III respectively.

Table No.1 Marketing cost and margins of Tomato (Rs/quintal)

Sr.No.	Particulars	Total Price		
		Channel I	Channel II	Channel III
A.	Marketing Cost incurred by Producers			
1	Grading, stitching, filling etc	15	15	24
2	Cost of packing	36	47	48
3	Transportation cost	24	25	35
4	Loading, unloading and wastage	7	12	11
5	Labour cost	76	0	0
6	Miscellaneous	13	0	0
7	Total Marketing Cost	171	99	118
8	Selling price of producer	1800	1600	1200
B.	Marketing Cost incurred by Wholesaler			
1	Market fee and development charge	0	0	32
2	Commission	0	0	75
3	Miscellaneous expenses	0	0	19
4	Total marketing cost	0	0	126
5	Market margin of wholesaler	0	0	130
C.	Market Cost Incurred by Retailer			
1	Transportation cost	0	26	7
2	Labour	0	11	12
3	Loss wastage and spoilage 3%	0	48	46
4	Rent of shop	0	8	4
5	Packing cost	0	0	6
6	Miscellaneous cost	0	16	10
7	Total marketing cost	0	109	85
8	Market margin of Retailer	0	347	211
9	Selling price of Retailer/Purchase price of consumer	1800	2056	1752

Price spread throughout the supply chain of Tomato vegetable.

The producer's share of revenue decreases as the number of intermediaries in the marketing channel increases. Table No.2 Outlined the price spread of Tomato in channel I the producers share in consumer rupee was 90.5 percent while the marketing cost incurred by producer's was 9.5 percent. The marketing cost incurred by Producer and Retailer in channel II was 5.30 percent, the price paid by the consumer was Rs.2056 /- quintal, in which producers share was 73

percent. The marketing cost incurred by Producer, Wholesaler and Retailer in channel III was 12.04 percent, the price paid by the consumer in channel III was Rs.1752/-quintal in which producers share was 61.75 percent. Highest market margin was observed in the channel III i.e 19.46 percent. A comparative analysis revealed that channel I was more profitable than channel II and channel III for marketing Tomatoes in Nagpur District.

Table No. 2 Price spread in marketing of Tomato

Sr.No.	Particulars	Total Price		
		Channel I	Channel II	Channel III
1	Net price received by producer	1629 (90.5)	1501 (73.00)	1082 (61.75)
2	Total marketing cost incurred by producer, wholesaler, retailer	171 (9.5)	109 (5.30)	211 (12.04)
3	Total market margin of wholesaler and retailer	0	347 (16.87)	341 (19.46)
4	Selling price of retailer/purchase price of consumer	1800 (100.00)	2056 (100.00)	1752 (100.00)

Marketing efficiency of Tomato across various marketing channels-

The marketing efficiency of Tomatoes across various channels was calculated using Acharya method with results presented in Table No.3

Represents marketing efficiency was higher in channel-I i.e 9.52 followed by channel II 3.29, and channel III 1.96 for the Tomato crop. The higher marketing margins taken by intermediaries in the channel II, and channel III hindered the efficiency of Tomato marketing.

Table No. 3 Marketing efficiency of Tomato

Sr.No.	Particulars	Channel I	Channel II	Channel III
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1	Consumers purchase price	1800	2056	1752
2	Producers sale price	1800	1600	1200
3	Total marketing cost	171	109	211
4	Total margins of intermediaries	-	347	341
5	Net price received by farmer	1629	1501	1082
6	Index of marketing efficiency			
a)	Acharya method	9.52	3.29	1.96

Constraints faced by producers in marketing of Tomatoes.

Selected vegetable producers were interviewed to gather insights on marketing obstacles. Important problems encountered by producers are detailed in Table No.4 Represents the marketing constraints faced by Tomato producers. All 10 producers reported that transportation costs

are high. 90 percent reported excessive fees by market middlemen followed by unmetalled roads 70 percent, packing material scarcity 50 percent, unethical labour practices 40 percent, and limited market facilities 20 percent.

Table No. 4 Marketing constraints faced by Tomato producers

Sr.No.	Constraints	No. of Farmers	Percent (n=10)
1	Transportation cost are high	10	100.00
2	Excessive fees by market middlemen	9	90.00
3	Unmetalled roads	7	70.00
4	Packaging material scarcity	5	50.00
5	Unethical labour practices	4	40.00
6	Limited market facilities	2	20.00

Expectations of consumers while purchasing Tomatoes.

Selected consumers were interviewed to gather information about their expectations, which are outline in the. Table No.5 Represents consumer expectations while purchasing Tomatoes. All 10 consumers reported

that Tomatoes should be blemish free, 80 percent reported that Tomato should be fresh followed by comparing Tomatoes by weight 60 percent, Tomatoes at affordable price 50 percent, colour of Tomatoes 30 percent, and tight Tomatoes with glossy appearance 20 percent

Table No. 5 Consumers expectations while purchasing Tomatoes

Sr.No.	Expectations	No. of Farmers	Percent (n=10)
1	Blemish-free Tomatoes	10	100.00
2	Tomatoes should be fresh	8	80.00
3	Compare Tomatoes by weight – the heavier ones are likely to be the juiciest.	6	60.00
4	Tomatoes at affordable prices	5	50.00
5	Colour :- red Tomatoes have strong flavour	3	30.00
6	Tight Tomatoes with glossy appearance	2	20.00

Conclusion

The selected vegetable was most commonly marketed through channel III (Producer –Wholesaler – Retailer -Consumer), among the three marketing channels evaluated. Producer's received the largest share of the consumer's rupee for Tomato in channel-I i.e 90.5 percent.Channel – I (Producer -Consumer) emerged as the most profitable marketing channel for selected vegetable in Nagpur District compared to channel II and channel III. The major constraints faced by Tomato producers overall level was transportation costs are high (100 percent), followed by excessive fees by market middlemen (90 percent), and unmetalled roads (70 percent). The major expectations reported by Tomato consumers overall level was blemish- free Tomato (100 percent) followed by Tomatoes should be fresh (80 percent) and comparing Tomatoes by weight (60 percent).

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Plate 1. Comparative efficacy of different botanicals against major seed-borne fungi of pearl millet

Table 3. Comparative efficacy of different botanicals against major seed-borne fungi of pearl millet

Sr. No	Botanicals	<i>Alternaria alternata</i>				<i>Rhizoctonia solani</i>				<i>Fusarium moniliforme</i>				Average			
		Mycelial growth (mm)*		Per cent growth inhibition *		Mycelial growth (mm)*		Per cent growth inhibition *		Mycelial growth (mm)*		Per cent growth inhibition *		Mycelial growth (mm)*		Per cent growth inhibition *	
		Concentration		Concentration		Concentration		Concentration		Concentration		Concentration		Concentration		Concentration	
		5%	10%	5%	10%	5%	10%	5%	10%	5%	10%	5%	10%	5%	10%	5%	10%
T1	Aloe vera	33.86	23.73	62.38	73.43	75.84	68.87	15.73	23.77	44.59	38.37	50.45	57.36	51.43	43.66	42.86	51.48
T2	Garlic	11.46	0.00	87.26	100	35.61	25.80	60.43	71.33	21.25	13.54	76.39	84.95	22.77	13.11	74.70	85.43
T3	Tulsi	39.63	20.17	55.96	77.27	70.48	56.33	21.28	37.46	49.44	41.77	45.06	53.59	53.18	39.42	40.91	56.20
T4	Neem	41.65	28.67	53.72	67.94	78.93	56.70	12.30	36.58	14.75	12.06	83.61	86.66	44.91	32.47	50.10	63.92
T5	Dhatura	28.76	19.57	68.04	78.02	26.73	19.53	70.30	77.88	26.79	23.44	70.23	73.96	27.42	20.84	69.53	76.84
T6	Control	90.00	90.00	-	-	90.00	90.00	-	-	90.00	90.00	-	-	90.00	90.00	-	-
	'F test	Sig.	Sig.	-	-	Sig.	Sig.	-	-	Sig.	Sig.	-	-	-	-	-	-
	SE(m)±	0.57	0.39	-	-	0.56	0.47	-	-	0.42	0.49	-	-	-	-	-	-
	CD(P=0.01)	2.32	1.59	-	-	2.27	1.90	-	-	1.72	2.01	-	-	-	-	-	-

*Mean of three replication

Fig. 1 Efficacy of botanicals against major seed-borne mycoflora of pearl millet at 5% concentration

Fig. 2 Efficacy of botanicals against major seed-borne mycoflora of pearl millet at 10% concentration